

The Representation of Women in African Literature: A Cross-Contemporary Perspective

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Abstract: As members of society, women have always been at the heart of literary creation. In African literature, authors have made different portrayals of women throughout history; depicting their perception of the African womanhood. Art in general and literature in particular are often deemed to be a reflection of reality; Hence the importance of studying the representation of African women in African literature. This research draws from two novels to analyze the image of women in African literature. It carries out a cross-contemporary analysis of the image of women, so as to understand progresses made during both periods. Results show that, women both post-independence and contemporary face similar challenges. But, it also appears from the analysis that, the contemporary African woman has new tools to use in her advantage; tools that, if well used, could help her emerge into a new African woman.

Keywords: African literature; Contemporary African women; African culture

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Introduction

In a paper discussing African literature, Onoge (1974 385-410) puts into perspective the fact that, African authors wanting to assert themselves and their literature in a postcolonial context have, for a majority, chosen an approach based on critical realism; i.e. "a literature committed to contemporary realism". In this vein, writers use their creative genius to paint the society and give an image of it from their perspective. Women as part of the African society have thus been at the center of many writing endeavors of African writers both male and female. Hence the many research papers, essays, anthologies analyzing both works of writers, the representation of women in African literature and the overall social impact of it (Kalu, 2020). Although researches analyzing the image of women in African literature through various works exist in numbers; they often use classics as corpus for their analyses. As a result, the representations from these works depict the African woman of the 80s. Therefore, it will be interesting to understand how African women are represented in contemporary literature from a cross-comparative perspective. In other words, how is the African

woman represented in contemporary literature? How is such representation similar or how does it differ from the African woman in post independence literature! This research draws on two novels by two African female writers to explore the representation of women in African literature, especially in post-colonial literature. It analyses the main themes represented in both novels, then explores what the differences or similarities in both novels in terms of representation of African women reveal about the evolution of their image in African literature and the society as a whole. This research is relevant in that; it takes a look at the representation of the African woman in different periods of history. The goal is to reveal either some progress or stagnation, reasons for such a situation and some possible solutions. The paper is divided into three main sections with some sections having subsections, and they are all considered in turn.

1. State of the art

The earliest record of a novel by an African woman writer dates back to 1967 with the Nigerian Writer Flora Nwapa's novel *Efuru*. Ever since, several other women writers have emerged and African literature by women continues to flourish. Besides, well before the emergence of a written literature, Africa boasts of an oral literature tradition that survived across centuries. A tradition in which, women were not left out. Both men and women have hence been depicting African society for centuries.

The arrival of African women writers in the literary world brought about a school of thought in research aimed at understanding the African woman as a person, as a writer through different lenses. In this vein, there are numerous papers, journal articles, anthologies revolving around the representation of African women in African literature. A review of the existing literature on this issue reveals some major trends that are discussed in turn. Despite the fact that, the image of women in African literature has long been a topic of research, the review focuses on more recent literature; especially works published in the 2000s onwards as they are more likely to reveal facts closest to the reality of the African woman today; as compared to the African woman in post-colonial Africa.

The first and probably most prominent category of research on the image of women in African literature are those focused on the position of female writers in African literature and the fact that, it is a reflection of the position of women in the African society as a whole. Such research often touches on topics such as: when women started writing, started accessing education, whether they were present in the portrayal of the society by writers before that or not; and if yes how they were represented.

Such research allows us to follow through the evolution of the image of women in African literature from early forms of literature such as: "orature"; later through the portrayal of western writers of African women and what such portrayal revealed of the image of women in the society of that time; then finally the portrayal by African male writers of African women; up till the emergence of African female writers and the impact of their coming into the arena.

In one article titled *Women's Literature in African History*, Kalu (2020) discusses the voice of the African woman throughout the literary history of Africa; stemming from the ages of African oral literature to the modern day African woman writer.

Indeed, the African woman had been present early on in retelling the African narrative in oral form. Yet, after the overtaking of western-style education, early on, only men were granted access to such education predominantly. This led to the constitution of an elite class of African men writers; who happen to represent the African woman through their lenses. Moreover, the belated emergence of African women writers led to women writers being perceived (rightfully so or not); as having a desire to correct what has been said not only by male African writers but also by early westerners' representing African women. On their part, following their natural progress, African women writers have

come to address issues out of the stereotypical socioeconomic context of the household wife and mother to “in-depth and inter-generational understandings about the lives and experiences of girls and African women”.

Yet, despite women writers emerging into an intellectual force in Africa and in the Diaspora, despite the establishing of major research journals and anthologies focusing on African women literature all this is still mainly available to the Diaspora. To the young African woman; that access is still not granted. This poses the issue of not being able to carry proper analysis of the image of the African woman across different periods of the history of Africa.

Sathyapriya (2020) gives another insight analyzing the image of women in African literature from ancient to modern period in an article titled: “Image of women in African literature”.

The author points out that, the image of women in literature has witness some evolution throughout different periods of African history. It went from the subservient, submissive mother in the precolonial era, the mainly exploited women by colonial capitalism during the colonial era, to witness some transformation that was only noticeable thereafter. Indeed, during the post colonial era, women in literature (and real life thereof) evolved into having more distinct personalities out of the nurturing mothers and wives they had been known as before. Two main conclusions are drawn from this article. First, women may have grown some personality and individuality; yet they still struggle to be autonomous and empowered. Secondly, this evolution is only visible because of the emergence of female African writers who were able to make women “appear in their true color and have distinct personality.” P166. These papers all center their analyses on the position of the African women writers and their evolution within the literary spectrum of African both oral and written literature. But, since literature is often a reflection of a given society at a given point in time, they allow us to witness the evolution of African women in different periods of history; thus giving us insights both from a literary and a realistic perspective.

Oyebolu (2022) analyses the emergence of women writers in francophone African literature. The main argument is that, women arrived in literature late. The reason for this is simply that, with the introduction of western style education, boys were the first to acquire education, while girls were expected to be raised for marriage. Therefore, early representations of African women in literature were those by male writers. Again, this analysis although based on the literary world can completely be mirrored on the reality of the African woman in society. After analyzing of the predominant themes discussed by the said authors, she concludes that, currently, “by focusing on the family, the corporate world and politics as it relates to women, African women writers are able to tell the stories of the African woman as insiders”. This argument brings into play another sub-theme also present in the literature about the image of women in African literature: that of; the difference in literature by men portraying African women and women portraying African women.

Indeed, this issue of the impact of gender on writing is not peculiar to African literature as; it constitutes an important part of the literary discourse. When they write, male writers portray society from their male experience. This often means when women write, they are said (rightfully so or not) to be trying to correct the worldview and the view on them portrayed by male writers. As a consequence, they might be automatically labeled feminists Lange (2008). In the case of African literature and the image of women, this is even more exacerbated as women writers emerged in the literary arena way later than their male counterparts. The first novel by a female African writer dates back to 1967. As far as francophone Africa is concerned Mariama Bâ's “*une si longue lettre*” published in 1981 is said to have paved the way for the emergence of even more female writers². However, the first novel by a woman from this area is; “*La grève des battus*” by Aminata Sow Fall.

Obviously, there are differences when men write about women and when women write about women. But it would be incongruous, even simplistic to say that; the experience of African women writers all boils down to a simple desire to

correct what men have said. It is even more simplistic to label them automatically as feminists just because they are women writers or writing about women.

Men and women do have different sensitivities and this certainly reflects in their writings. As a result, the image of women portrayed by African women writers in their writings is a reflection of their experience as members of the African society; a society that like any other; has issues that need to be addressed. Also, writing is art and more often than not, art draws from the reality of the artist, both the immediate and the hoped reality. This approach in literature is known as the sociological approach. It focuses on the social function of literature, and considers any piece of writing as by definition written for an audience which is part of society hence for a society.²

Moreover, the idea of women African writers writing to correct what male counterparts have said before or it being for the sole purpose of claiming back a position they might have lost is also problematic in that, this makes the African woman's narrative predominantly a colonial creation. That is, women only started telling stories after they accessed western style education. This couldn't be farther from the truth. Indeed, before writers started using colonial languages to record the African narrative, oral literature has existed for centuries in Africa transmitted through generations in forms of tales, poems, epics, proverbs. Needless to say, women have always been part of this literary culture referred to as "orature".

In all, African women writers are full fledged artists free to take their writing endeavor towards which ever paths their creative genius draws them. It just so happens to often be about denouncing the injustices they encounter in their society. But it could also be romance, fantasy or any other literary trope... The African female writer is not to be put into boxes simply because she wants to use her voice to echo that of other women.

The second and probably most abundant category of literature on the representation of women in African literature is that which centers on analyzing different novels or authors so as to bring out the portrayal of women in each work. First, we have those analyzing one novel, so as to discuss the various themes discussed therein and, also cast the analysis onto the current social context. There is also, research that analyzes two or more novels with the same purpose. These analyses often revolve around challenges facing women in the African society as a whole. Finally, there are those drawn from completely different social context in terms of culture, or in terms of religion. In these analyses, they showcase how women in the novel and thus in the society still face blatant discrimination because of some rules of religion, or simply some deleterious aspects of African culture.

Another trend in these types of research papers is analyzing novels written by male writers with African women as main characters or simply as characters; so as to understand how African male writers and male in general see women; but also evaluate the impact of such a representation. After exploring this types of reviews, it is clear that, many post-colonial writers had female main characters and there are commonalities in the way they presented them: the household woman wholesomely dedicated to her family, the woman with the desire to, or seen as emancipated (because she adopts western codes of behavior), the unhappy woman broken by the weight of the religion of tradition but who remains submissive etc. Basically, women are often presented by these writers as victims. Considering there has to be a perpetrator to be a victim, one is left to question why the latter is never addressed by these male writers...

After reviewing and analyzing the existing literature about the representation of women in African literature, some interesting facts can be drawn. There is: those analyzing female writers and their position in the literary world, those who see the position of women writers as a reflection of that of African women in society, those who analyze novels so as to link up fiction to reality and shed light on challenges facing African women in both the traditional and the modern world. Also, there is a tendency to curb the creative genius of the African female writer; by automatically putting her

in boxes, thereby downplaying her achievements as a writer. No matter the perspective, it is clear that, there is a tendency in research to link up fiction to reality in order to analyze the African woman's experience in her society.

However, we found that, only few studies to none compared two novels from different periods of history such as the 60s Vs the 2010s or upward. This is relevant in that, fiction mostly reflects the reality of the time during which it was written. Therefore, analyzing two novels from completely different periods in the history of African society will allow witnessing progress made in terms of addressing the issues facing African women. The argument is that, an African woman from post colonial Africa had some challenges that a young African woman currently may no more have. Or if the latter does; then, there is room to question the pace at which the African society is improving. It will be interesting therefore, to analyze such progress.

This paper does just that. That is, it analyses two novels from completely different eras in the development of the African woman. One is set in the 80s barely 20 years after the independence of most African countries, whilst the other is from a current female author. The focus is on the similarities and the differences in both novels; and most importantly, what such similarities or differences reveal about the current situation of the African woman.

2. The novels

2.1. "*Une si longue lettre*" (So long a letter) by Mariama Bâ, 1979

Mariama Bâ is a Senegalese novelist and activist born in 1929 in Dakar and death in 1981. During her career as a writer, she penned two novels "*Une si longue lettre*" (So long a letter) 1979 and "*Le chant écarlate*" (The Scarlet Song) 1981. The former which is the one of the corpuses to the present study, has gained recognition from the literary world as a top tier novel from the post colonial period, and as a classic in African literature as a whole. It has been translated into several languages. But, the present study draws from the original French version, English translations are provided for direct citations.

"*Une si longue lettre*" is about Ramatoulaye, a woman who just lost her husband and is currently undergoing traditional and religious rites of widowhood. She receives a letter from her friend Aïssatou, then undertakes to reply by also writing a long letter in which she recounts all the turmoil she has been going through following the death of her husband. She also recalls their youthful days; When Aïssatou and her were young, newly graduates, full of hope, eager to embrace a political life, and an active career. But life has taken them on completely different paths. Here they are today, Ramatoulaye on her part lost her husband. But before dying, he has already been "death" to her and their 12 children. The moment Modou Fall decided to marry a younger girl, Bineta just to feel young again, life had not been the same for Ramatoulaye. Overnight, she saw her life change completely going from a happy household, a fulfilling family life to having to endure polygamy first, and now widowhood. Aïssatou on her part was betrayed by her husband who also remarried and did not care that he hurt her. But she didn't settle, she exiled to the US and engaged in a professional career.

In this 170 pages novel, Mariama Bâ tackles amongst others, issues such as polygamy, forced marriage, the weight of religion and some deleterious aspects of traditions.

2.2. "*Les impatientes*" (The impatient: a novel) by Djâïli Amadou Amal, 2020

Djâïli Amadou Amal is a Cameroonian novelist born in 1975 to a Cameroonian father and an Egyptian mother. Early on, she harbors the dream of becoming a novelist and has, through hard work made her dream come true. So far in her career, she has authored several novels such as "*Walaande ou l'art de partager un mari*", 2010; "*Mistiirijo, la mangeuse*

d'âme", 2013; "Munyal, les larmes de la patience", 2017 and her latest novel "Coeur du Sahel", published in 2022. "Les impatientes" (The Impatient: a novel), 2020 is an updated version of *Munyal*. It is so far her most successful novel. It was shortlisted in the "Prix Goncourt" the most prestigious French-speaking literary prize, and ended up being awarded in the category "Prix Goncourt des lycéens".

In "les impatientes", we follow three women Ramla, Hindou and Safira; with apparently different yet very similar fates. Ramla the main character who voices the story, is 17 she was promised in marriage to Aminou, a boy of her generation with whom she is in love. They have plans together as she is walking towards successfully completing her final year in high school and pursue her dream of becoming a pharmacist. But, everything changes the day her mother, devastated, announces to her that she has just been given in marriage by her uncle to a man much older than her; but affluent and influential. It is the beginning of long episodes of misfortune for the young girl who never surrenders to her fate and fight all her strengths to escape this unlikely marriage. This is not the case for her sister, Hindou, same age as her. The latter was married on the same day as Ramla to a cousin of theirs. This cousin (and husband) struggles with several addictions such as alcohol, pornography, drugs. Hindou, will become the ultimate victim to the consequences of these addictions as she eventually suffers a severe depression.

In this soul crushing novel inspired by real life events, the author pens stories that women in this society under the influence of religious beliefs all live with.

3. Discussion and interpretation

3.1. The African woman and her fate through marriage

One blatant issue highlighted in both novels is that of marriage; and most importantly the fate of women in marriage. Often times, it comes in form of forced marriage, polygamy, unhappy household situations. Many causes can explain this situation; the main causes being religion and some traditions. Both novels are set up within societies where religion allows men to have more than one spouse and also grant them with many other privileges as compared to women. The latter's voices are seldom considered, let alone heard.

Forced marriage is a recurring situation in both novels. It is mostly very young women, barely out of teenage that are bound to obey to their parents by marrying complete strangers. In "les Impatientes", we have the main character Ramla and her sister Hindou. Ramla is 17 in her final year of high school, about to graduate. She wants to move on to study and become a pharmacist. As most girls of her age, she has a boyfriend, same age. But, her world crumbles when her uncle gives her hand to another man and her mother is the one to announce it to her.

Hindou on the other hand, is given into marriage to her cousin Moubarak, a young 22 years old boy alcoholic and addicted to pornography, and drugs that have been consuming him. This marriage is actually an opportunity for his father to get rid of him, and the burden of dealing with his troubles. During the wedding Hindou falls to the ground crying and begging her dad not to give up on her as she is not even in love with the cousin she is marrying. Both girls insist expressing their grieves and the fact that the future husbands are complete strangers to them and they do not love them. But, all their tears are met with injunctions to patience and obedience, in order to be good wives according to religion and tradition. « *Patience, mes filles ! Munyal ! Telle est la seule valeur du mariage et de la vie. Telle est la vraie valeur de notre religion, de nos coutumes, du pulaaku.* » ("Patience, my daughters! Munyal! This is the true value of marriage and life. This is the true value of our religion, our customs, and the pulaaku.") Page 7.

Another important cause of forced marriage is social position. That is in some cases, besides religion and tradition; marriage represents an opportunity to the families of the young girls to obtain better social status. In "Une si longue lettre", Bineta is a young high school teenager who ends up marrying Modou Fall, who is none other than the father of

her best friend. This wedding is an opportunity to her mother who, because of the caste society is considered of a lower social class. But, by giving her daughter in marriage to Modou, she immediately rises socially.

Ramla marries Aladji Issa, a business partner of her father and her uncle. When he asks to marry Ramla, the uncle and the dad cannot say no because; such an alliance will be great for business. Apart from being an affluent businessman, the biggest in the whole town, he is a politician and could influence tax collectors to push on the family's businesses if they refuse to give their daughter into marriage to him. Therefore, Ramla will marry this man encouraged by her mother as she announces to her and points out the importance of such a wedding: *"Tu es trop jeune pour comprendre l'importance d'une telle alliance. Dans un mariage, on ne recherche pas que l'amour. Le plus important pour une femme est d'être à l'abri du besoin. Protégée, adulée."* ("You are too young to understand the importance of such an alliance. Love is not the sole purpose of marriage. The most important thing for a woman is to be free from want. Protected, adored.") Page 23.

In all these instances, it is religion, tradition or social status that is at play. Parents, both mothers and fathers give the girl child in marriage. In some cases, the decision is taken and the mother just has to adhere and even support the father's decision by convincing the girl. After all, they are only wives themselves, and have to be obedient and submissive even if the decision is harming their own children. Besides, in *"Les impatientes"*, Ramla points out that, her mother bore 10 children. She describes the fact that, she always looked beautiful clean and well dressed. She looked happy although in hindsight, she resented everything life has put her through. She resented living in the polygamist household and looking at her family decline right in front of her eyes. Yet, she couldn't and wouldn't do anything, as she is too afraid of being divorced from: *« Elle le trouve injuste mais n'a aucune envie de finir répudiée. Protection oblige ! »*. ("She finds it unfair but, since she has no desire to end up repudiated, she opts for protection!") Page 17. In Bineta's case, the greedy mother sees in her young girl's wedding, the opportunity to become someone in the materialistic society, and jumps on it by "selling" her young daughter in "marriage".

Subsequently, all those rules of religion and tradition that lead to forced marriage result for many cases in unhappy households. Not only for the wedded girls, but also in some cases the first wives. Safira in *"Les impatientes"* decides to stay in her marriage just so she can dedicate her whole time to fighting the young Ramla and making life even more difficult for her than it already is. She goes to extends such as, stilling money from her husband just so they can turn around and accuse Ramla. This brings in another scenario; Ramatoulaye, Safira, and Aïssatou where in a seemingly happy household until the husband decides to marry a younger woman. The reactions are different in each case; Ramatoulaye decides to stay for the kids, Aïssatou lives to the US. No matter the reactions here, we can still notice the fact that, the decisions are barely guided by the free wills of women themselves. There is this ever running notion of making important life decisions based on exterior factors and not what they would have done by will.

Marriage also has a significant impact on women's physical and mental health in both novels. In *"les impatientes"*, Ramla's mother has bore 10 children in total. In *"Une si longue lettre"* on the other hand, Ramatoulaye bore 12 children in 20 years of marriage. This insane number of children by one single woman; although not biologically impossible obviously leave consequences on the physiognomy of the mother. Be it back issues, or even more gynecologic health issues. Not to mention the mental space it takes for one person to raise so many children by herself. Ramla, under the pressure of and the turmoil the first wife has been putting on her, ends up having a miscarriage during yet another fight and false accusations orchestrated by her.

The mental toll marriage and all its difficulties takes on women are portrayed in both novels through depression. In *"les impatientes"*, it is through Hindu who married her cousin. After enduring all kinds of mistreatment, she ends up sinking into a severe depression which is automatically assumed to be "craziness" as she comments: *« J'ai changé. On dit que je suis malade. Peut-être que c'est vrai. Je ne sais pas. J'ai changé. Maintenant, j'entends des voix. J'ai changé. On dit que je*

suis possédée. Qu'un djinn malveillant me hante... On dit que je suis folle et que j'ai changé. » ("I have changed. They say I'm sick. Maybe that's true. I don't know. I have changed. Now I hear voices. I have changed. They say I'm possessed. That some malevolent jinn haunt me... They say that I am crazy and that I have changed.") Page 78-80.

In "*Une si longue lettre*", Jacqueline is the Ivorian woman, Christian who married a Muslim Senegalese. In Senegal, she is considered of a lower social group by her in laws. They despise her because she refuses to convert to Islam. Plus, being a foreigner, she faced lots of comments on that as well. She is ostracized, despised and mocked for simply being from a different culture. So much so that, she ends up in a psychiatric clinic where she tries to explain what is actually happening to her.

In all, the African woman in both novels is portrayed as a victim through marriage. She is victim in that; she has to endure marriage and all it implies for her. She has to submit to what religion and some traditions have set her to be as a woman; no matter what toll it takes on her physical and mental health. The African woman in this lens, is not an entity able to take her own decisions; even as important decisions as choosing a partner. She is voiceless, not listened to and has most of her fate imposed upon her; imposed by religious beliefs or by some traditions. Often times, she either surrenders and accepts this fate, or then undertakes actions against all odds in order to defy tradition, religion, elders and reverse this fate.

3.2. the African woman against all odds

In both novels, education: western education more precisely is often presented as a way for the African woman to emancipate. It is the eye opener and her key to freedom. This is also the case with any tool or concept from the western lifestyle.

In "*les impatientes*", Ramla's desire to finish high school and study to become a pharmacist constitutes a big drive to her. Education also allows women to express their political commitment as Ramatoulaye and Aïssatou discuss the almost absence of women in politics in Senegal 20 years after independence. From this perspective, education grants the African woman with a voice. She can finally express herself, somehow.

This explains why in both novels, girls' pursuing formal education is received with mixed feelings to total hostility by men. They unanimously believe there is no need for girls to pursue education. Ramla's mother is castigated for letting her daughter pursue education until she is about to graduate from high school. Binetou in "*une si longue lettre*" is pulled out of school so she can marry Modou Fall. To her mother, marrying an older and richer man is an opportunity that does not compare with acquiring education.

Yet, this idea of education being a way out for the African woman is questionable. In "*Une si longue lettre*" education was not the way through for Ramatoulaye as she had already studied and even worked as a teacher. She still decided to stay and raise her 12 children on her own because, she did not see herself other than a wife and a mother. Plus, Modou Fall having abandoned her to go and live with his young wife, it seems to be the obvious option for her and to all women who find themselves in this predicament. In this society, children are always a choice beyond what the woman wants to do. Men on the other hand are free to let go of their families overnight and not face any criticism.

Of course, education gives those women choice. But, in some situations, they did not choose education even if they could have, simply because of their natural role of bearing and nurturing children. Education is just an option as choice in the case of the African women; it is a double edge sword. When choosing one thing, she often has to sacrifice the other. Therefore, education is an option, not a miracle solution. At least in the cases discussed here.

On another note, there are other symbols of emancipation worth analyzing in both novels. Aïssatou having found out her husband got another wife did not surrender to that faith. She instead, left and went to the US to pursue a professional career. Ramla does same when; helped by her elder brother and her boyfriend, she plots and escape her household, move to Yaoundé where she will be free to take on her ambitions of becoming a pharmacist. Departing is seen as one way for them to start over in a place where their voices can be heard; in a place and culture more tolerant towards them, supposedly. Same goes for Ramatoulaye who is gifted a car by her friend. The car here symbolizes mobility and the idea of finding her autonomy and ultimately moving.

Finally, the internet in "*Les impatientes*" is another interesting symbol of emancipation. Ramla had been communicating with her brother and her boyfriend through the internet, and this is how she was able to plan and eventually escape to Yaoundé. Besides, she was also taking an online course towards the projects she has been endearing. We can see here that; the internet and new technologies on a bigger picture are presented as a way for African women to overcome the odds set against them by society.

3.3. Two novels, two eras, same challenges for African women

A comparative analysis of both novels shows that, although one is set some 20 years after the Independences and the other some 70 years thereafter, the image of the African woman as portrayed in both novels still shows lots of similarities.

The African woman is mainly portrayed as a victim. A victim of domestic violence against women, forced marriage, polygamy, religious and cultural constrains. Society does not grant her with that many options. She is forced into marriage and denied education; she is summoned to be submissive and endure all the ill treatments by both husbands and families. Even as she stays, she may be confronted with having to raise her children alone with a husband completely absent from their lives. She is constrained; by traditions, by religion, by the society; a society in which her voice is seldom heard. For example, during the wedding ceremony in "*Les impatientes*" the girls are pleading to their fathers and uncles, crying their eyes out so they are not given into marriage to men they do not love. But pleads fall on deaf ears as Uncle Hayatou is busy unrolling a string of injunctions to the girls; A list of things that they ought to do in order to be deemed good wives according to both religion and tradition. When not under all these injunctions, the African woman will still be met with big dilemmas. Women who stand by family values and will do everything to keep their family united or flat out please relatives are an interesting case of such dilemmas. Ramatoulaye decided to stay in a polygamist marriage, something she actually despises, so she could raise her 12 children alone. Ramla's Mother is said to have marry her husband just to help release the sorrows of her parents after the loss of their beloved daughter. Despite everything, these women went through; they are rooting for their families and the importance of family; as it is the basis to any healthy foundation. This portrayal of the African woman as one who values family does apply not only to the characters in our analyses, but to the African society as a whole. Indeed, it is worth noting that, lots of African women still choose to stay in unhappy marriages because they won't sacrifice the future of their children, their family. This situation brings mixed feelings. On one hand, sacrificing for the greater good -that of the children- is commendable; but on the other hand, it still boils down to the African woman's voice, desires, and aspirations being silenced and put after everyone else'. A huge dilemma indeed!

These similarities in terms of experiences in novels set so apart in history brings us to question the society. In other words, how can a girl child from the 80s and another from the 2000s relate so much in terms of experiences? A reason for such stagnation can be found in hindering believes of religion for example, where the girl child is considered lesser a child compared to her male brother. Giving that African societies are still very much under the influence of imported religious beliefs, they play a part in perpetuating these stereotypes.

On the ground, there obviously have been lots of improvements in terms of girls' access to education. But old beliefs linked to religion and some cultural beliefs still hinder such progress. The constant absorption of the western way of life and way of thinking is also a cause to this stagnation. As we discussed, any society is bound to create its own fitted model, it could be by getting inspiration from other societies, but not by copying to the point of losing one's uniqueness. Otherwise it leads to a chaotic situation where, foreign religion, foreign lifestyle coupled with bad aspects of the local culture all come together to hinder social progress.

In all, challenges are virtually the same in both novels for women in the sense that, there is this assumption that she has to choose career over motherhood, face an unhappy marriage anyway, and many other odds set against her simply because of her being a female.

3.4. A new dawn for the African woman

Having discussed all the similar aspects of the two novels and why they had similarities despite being set way apart in history, there are some interesting progresses in the image of the African woman that can be pointed out. In both novels, the young girls victims of forced marriage have completely different reactions to their fate, in "*Une si longue lettre*", where Binetou and Nabou stayed submissive and stay into marriage they did not want, Ramla in "*Les impatientes*" fought with her last energy. Most importantly, she fought with modern tools in her environment until she was able to escape that fate.

On one hand, there is her use of the internet. She used the internet as a way through. On the other hand, she was helped both by her brother and her boyfriend. By using technologies such as the internet, they were able to free Ramla of this polygamous wedding and get her to escape to Yaoundé. Indeed, Ramla's brother would have been expected as a man to adhere to this idea of women not having the right to education and being forced into polygamist unions at a young age. But as a young boy of the 2000s his mentality is different. Such that, he helps his sister escape from her forced marriage. This moment is symbolic; this is a sign, a new dawn for African women. One in which they put themselves into predicaments that can help them escape the turmoil of society. They not only use modern tools, but also, they walk hand in glove with their men towards building stronger foundation for the African society. In this new society, men and women work as a team to eradicate bad aspects of their culture, use the new tools to empower each other in building better relationship and happier families.

We believe that, this could be a starting point to a new era in the African society; one where men and women actually partner up. The new African woman needs a new African man, just like Ramla's brother to see her through her challenges, protect her, and assist her, team up with her in building a solid family dynamic with love patience, mutual understanding and mutual respect as foundations.

In this new era, there is no place for feminism because, if feminism was once a solution to some problems of that time, it is obvious that it has stopped being one, at least in the case of the African woman. And if anything, it is actually hindering a conversation towards actual solutions that will include both parties. A conversation based on the desire by both men and women to understand each other's' struggles and walk towards a stronger family dynamic which constitutes the basis of any healthy society so far.

Conclusion

To sum up, this research intended to examine the image of women in African literature using two novels from different eras of the history of Africa. It revealed that, due to the influence of religion and to some extend traditions, women are still victims of practices of forced marriage, denied access to education. They are portrayed mainly as submissive victims with no voice.

A comparison of the main protagonists in each novel revealed that, the modern African woman does not remain victim and submissive but instead uses tools such as internet to fight her way out of the oppression she is facing. It also revealed that, education and the drive to get formal education and pursue a career do affect the attitude of the woman facing all those discriminations. In some cases, it makes her even more eager to get out of her situation. Although in some cases, education is yet another option but which she cannot choose and chooses her children instead. Moreover, in the new generation, the African woman can count on men helping her. Men who do not see her as only meant for marriage and that do not deserve education. These results are very interesting in that; it is a sign that there is some little change in the society. The African woman can now count on men and technologies to help her fight the odds set against her in the society.

Although it is true that some aspects of African traditions and cultures oppress the woman, not everything in African culture is bad and to be thrown away. By this we mean that, solutions to challenges facing African women are not going to come out of neither feminism nor any other forms of western philosophy being pushed on the contemporary woman. Neither is the solution going to be fighting each other (men and women) using tools inadequate to the African society.

The solution lies in the modern African woman and the modern African man coming together to strip the tradition of its bad aspects, build an armature against negative influence from the western society, engage in actual conversations based on the desire to understand their struggles. And use the tools offered by the globalized modern society to build a stronger family nucleus rooted in crucial values of African culture which is family. It would be interesting to further look into ICTs and the relationship African women have with this. In other words, how does

ICTs help women finding and redefining their identity as African women, in as much as this may set a new dawn in her fate as it was seen in this paper. Further studies could focus on that. Another important point is that, both novels analyzed here are set in societies utterly influenced by Islam. The challenges women face in such societies are different from that of women from other religious backgrounds. Therefore, it will be interesting to carry out an analysis of two novels from religiously different social contexts.

Notes

① Post independence literature refers to literary production after the independence of African countries which started in 1957 with Ghana gaining back its independence from Britain and several other African countries following suit throughout the 60s. These countries joined Liberia and Ethiopia as the last two have never experience colonial rule.

② Orature: The Oxford Dictionary of Literary terms define Orature as:

“A portmanteau term coined by the Kenyan novelist and playwright Ngugi Wa Thiong’o to denote imaginative works of the oral tradition usually referred to as “oral literature”. The point of the coinage is to avoid suggesting that oral compositions belong to a lesser or derivative category.”

③ Though not exactly the first novel published by a francophone female writer, Mariama Bâ’s “*une si longue lettre*” is considered to have pioneered women’s literature as it helped shine the light on a then unseen group of writers.

④ This concept is developed by American sociologist Kenneth Burke.

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